

From Research to Action: 18 months of research on the Video Games Industry Ecosystem & Strategic Recommendations for policymakers

Summary

GAMEHEARTS is an EU Horizon funded project examining the value of the European Video Game Industry Ecosystem (EVGIE) and its importance in contributing to economic growth, job creation, physical and mental wellbeing, and social and cultural cohesion. As part of the project's remit GAMEHEARTS partners at Wroclaw University of Economics and Business have identified mechanisms of value transfer and value co-creation by EVGIE and wider Creative and Cultural Industries. Their findings provide insight into the merits of cooperation and ascertains key recommendations to alleviate tensions in the process of inter-sector partnerships.

Research Design

As part of the **GAMEHEARTS project** (gamehearts.eu), an intensive and methodologically diverse research process was conducted to examine the functioning of the European ecosystem surrounding the video game industry. The course of this process is outlined below. Through the QR codes, you can access the full reports from specific research stages.

Literature analysis & case studies	Quantitative Survey	In-depth qualitative interviews	Focus group interviews	Design thinking-based marathons
<p>Data: 61 academic articles, 55 industry reports, and 18 statistical reports from the Statista database, 3 major & 6 minor cases</p> <p>Thematic scope: Co-creation of value, value transfer, co-innovation, 3E & 4E model of cooperation</p>	<p>Data: 1270 of European video game developers</p> <p>Thematic scope: level, scope, phases of co-creation & co-innovation relationships, innovativeness level, impact of co-innovation relationships on innovativeness of VGDs</p>	<p>Data: 27 interviews with representatives from EVGIE and CCI</p> <p>Thematic scope: impacts of VGI, cross-industry cooperation, strategic recommendations</p>	<p>Data: 1 national & 1 international focus group interview (8 game developers)</p> <p>Thematic scope: 5 insights from prior research steps investigated</p>	<p>Data: 3 national & 1 international edition (72 practitioners from EVGIE & CCI, 12 working teams)</p> <p>Thematic scope: cross-industry cooperation across 4E model, strategic recommendations</p>
<p>State of the Art Report</p>				

Recommendations for policymakers

Area	Recommendations for policymakers		Beneficiaries	
			Direct	Indirect
Awareness building	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Build managerial and business awareness of openness, innovation, and ecosystems, and foster mutual understanding for effective collaboration. Promote methodological transparency, rigour, and consistent communication across industry reporting and practice. 		VGD CCI	Economy
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote inclusive and accessible cultural experiences, not only in terms of gender or origin, but also, for example, economic factors. 		Society	VGD CCI
Infrastructure development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create online spaces for contact and matchmaking. Facilitate information exchange, training, and support for cross-industry collaboration. Develop or support online platforms, on-site hubs, clusters, and templates for cross-sector networking. Provide cooperation platforms, tool repositories, databases, IP systems, contract templates, documentation, and case-study libraries. Support joint research through shared hubs with infrastructure and expert resources. Appoint cooperation ambassadors and cross-industry project facilitators. 		VGD CCI	Economy
Funding	Scope & Targets	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support games and game applications in a culture focused on European/national cultural heritage. Preserve games as cultural heritage. Fund creativity-embedded formats: residencies, bootcamps, creative labs, design thinking marathons. Encourage investment in transmedia-ready intellectual properties. 	VGD CCI	Culture Economy Customers Economy
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adapt funding frameworks to VGI asymmetries (e.g., design funding schemes tailored for small and emerging studios, as well as indie studios). Promote utilisation of co-innovation relationships with the institutional microenvironment and with industries focused on cultural expansion. 	VGD	Customers Economy CCI
	Institutional changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adopt a participatory and open approach to policy & funding programmes design (e.g., invite experienced practitioners). 	Founder	VGD CCI
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cut bureaucracy by simplifying documentation and reducing the number of decision-makers, ensuring those involved understand the video-game and creative industries. Require transparent progress reporting for publicly funded projects, including successes, failures, lessons learned, and use of standard templates. 	VGD CCI	Founder
Law & regulations	Adoption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement coherent and future-oriented AI policies, recommendations, and creative but ethical reuse rules. 	VGD CCI	Economy
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop a comprehensive EU-wide approach to video games preservation. Introduce sound tax reliefs coherent across Europe. 	VGD	Culture Society Economy
	Amendment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Institutionalise VGD–CCI cooperation in public policy. Intensify actions aimed at facilitating OA to digital and non-digital culture. 	VGD CCI	Economy Society
	Enhancement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improve and harmonise legal frameworks related to ownership and IP licensing regulations for creative reuse. Clarify and make regulations more transparent, including clear definitions of basic terms such as "European game" or "video game developer." Deregulate, simplify laws, and accelerate legislative processes and necessary adjustments. 	VGD CCI	Economy

Further Information

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